

Teaching numbering within a hundred in elementary math classes (based on independent study)

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Abstract:

Elementary school math lessons are based on what children learned in previous courses when teaching numbers to 100. New pedagogical technologies and teaching aids have been used to explain this topic to children.

EASIJ

Accepted 15 August 2020

Published 20 August 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3993779

Keywords: numbering, arithmetic, concentration, technology, verbal numbering, automation, comparison,

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Introduction

In the elementary mathematics course, material on numbering and arithmetic operations is studied in concentrates. Elementary math involves working on a total of five concentrations. These are concentrations of decimals, decimals, hundreds, thousands, and multi-digit numbers.

Each concentrate reflects the main issues of the systematic arithmetic course according to its content, so as students learn to number numbers within one or another range and to operate on these numbers, the essence of arithmetic in general is clear. they imagine.

Each time new numbers are numbered on the basis of material and repeated references in the performance of operations, the most important, allows to deepen and expand the content of arithmetic concepts. In addition, the gradual formation of sound learning and skills (in numbers, measurements, oral and written numbering, calculations, etc.) is ensured, as the methods of performing these actions are gradually strengthened, while maintaining commonality.

Main part

The reasons for studying the second decade separately are as follows:

1. Students gain an initial understanding of the decimal structure of a number, where they first learn about the existence of a decimal number.
2. Addition and subtraction operations on one-digit integers (in terms of the methods of performing them) are actually completed in the second decimal, because, for example, addition and subtraction within 100 are performed using the methods used in the second decimal concentration.
3. The addition and subtraction table ends in the first 2 decimal places, so it must be automated.

Elementary school math lessons rely on what children have learned in previous courses to teach them to number out of 100.

New pedagogical technologies and teaching aids can be used to explain this topic to children.

When teaching numbering in the face, the lesson will be more understandable if it is done on a demonstration basis.

Learn to number in the second decimal place.

Preparatory work for teaching the numbering of the second decimal place is carried out during the preparation of the material on the topic "The first ten". For this purpose, exercises are included to count things in decimals (how many students are in row 1? How many students are in row 2? How many students are there in total in the class? Etc.). It is helpful to include a few exercises to count groups of objects (a pair of shoes, a pair of buttons, a set of five buttons, etc.) to help children move on to counting decimals.

It is also used as a prep exercise to say the name of the second decimal number: what number is said after two in the count, after twelve? before five, before fifteen? What is the result of adding one to 3? What about adding 1 to 13? Which number is smaller than 5 by 1 (less)? and so on.

Although such exercises can be solved by only a few students in the class, all children are assured that there are numbers after the first ten, which are many, and that there is a

similarity with the names of numbers that children are familiar with when naming these consecutive numbers.

The children learned to identify which of the numbers being compared was greater and which was smaller when they studied the first decimal (they conclude that the number that comes later in the count is greater than the number that comes first).

In addition to comparing numbers in the first decimal place, the teacher should “apply” this knowledge in the application of 20. For example, look at the number ladder. How many cubes are there on the first one? (one). What about the end? (ten). How many cubes should there be on the next (next) column if we continue the step of numbers? (eleven). What's next? (Twelve). Such questions can be asked: “Which number is bigger: 4 or 5? Guess which number is bigger: 14 or 15?”

Verbal numbering. The study of verbal numbering of second decimal numbers begins with the formation of the concept of decimals. The teacher ties the sticks in tens and shows how to make tens from one. The children do the same exercises, and then they count, add, and subtract decimals. For example, how many dozen sticks did they tie in this row? Put three more dozen sticks on the table than mine. As a result of such exercises, children conclude that decimals can be counted, added, and subtracted as simple units (ones). Then, based on counting ones and tens, the formation of 10-20 numbers is considered and their names are explained.

Teacher: There is 1 ten or 10 sticks here. How do you get the number after ten?

Student: Add one to ten?

Teacher: Look, I'm going to put one stick on top of ten - ten and one. How much are the sticks?

Student: A total of 11 sticks.

Teacher: How many tens (ten) and how many ones in eleven?

Student: One ten and one one.

Then the knowledge of the decimal structure of numbers is strengthened with and without visual aids.

1) List 12 sticks and determine how many sticks there are and how many sticks there are.

2) Take 1 dozen sticks and 4 more sticks - how many sticks did we get in total?

In the study of verbal numbering and later written numbering, addition and subtraction are considered, which are the division of numbers into round additions.

We add 10 units, 9 ones, and the result is 1 ten and 9 units.) Such exercises bring the decimal structure of numbers to consciousness and its organization.

For example, solve examples; $10 + 9$, $17 - 10$, (explanation: 10 this also allows you to master 1 ten or.

The formation of numbers in the natural order, their quantitative and ordinal relations are determined by performing the following exercises:

1) Count one by one from 12, say the numbers that are formed, count one by one from 20 and vice versa, and say the numbers that are formed.

2) 1 greater than 17 (say a small number).

3) Solve examples orally. $13 + 1$, $18 - 1$, $14 \text{ cm} - 1 \text{ cm}$, $19 \text{ cm} + 1 \text{ cm}$,

Add and subtract within 100

According to the program, when learning to add and subtract numbers within 100, students should not only learn the methods of calculation for all cases of addition and subtraction, but also acquire certain theoretical knowledge. They are the interrelationships between the components and the result of adding a number to a sum, adding a sum to a number, subtracting a sum from a sum, subtracting a sum from a sum, and adding and subtracting.

Children are first introduced to parentheses. In order to prepare to enter parentheses, the teacher prepares 2 cards for two or three expressions.

For example, $7 + (8 + 5)$ prepares two cards for the expression (2 out of 2) $y 8 + 5$ and $7 + 13$. The teacher puts an $8 + 5$ card on the deck. It means to read the text using the word "sum": calculate the sum.

"Now add 7 to the sum of 8 and 5." (Cards with numbers + and 7 are placed on the deck board ($13 + 7 = 20$)). After such preparation, the teacher introduces the children to the brackets.

Guys, we need to add 2 to the difference between 8 and 3. Look at this card. What this post means. (Difference between numbers 8 and 3). Let's add 2 to this difference. (puts a + sign, puts a card with the number 2 on a white background). Calculate the difference. (5 is generated.). add 2 to the difference. How much will it cost? (7). Writes an example. We don't have an $8-3$ card, so I'm going to circle the difference between 8 and 3 with a circle of $8-3$. (wraps the resulting $8-3$ record: $(8-3)$ I add 2 to this subtraction. (+ writes the sign and the number 2;) this entry is formed: $(8-3) + 3$). Please read again. (Add 2 to the difference between 8 and 3).

When writing such entries in a notebook, only part of the circle is drawn without drawing the top and bottom, leaving only the parentheses. The parentheses mean that you must first find the difference between the numbers 8 and 3, and then add the two.

For example, looking at the first note $(5 + 2) + 1 = 8$ and the pictures given to the problem, the children read the left side of the example (add 1 to the sum of the numbers 5 and 2) and explain how each number is described. (The first addition represents 5 rubber balls, the second 2 footballs, and the number to be added represents 1 children's ball). Then exercises are given to apply the properties of substituting two adjacent conjunctions with their sum, which prepares them to master the methods of calculation. For example, it is convenient to replace two adjacent conjunctions with their sum. Calculate by the method: $5 + 9 + 1$, $3 + 14 + 6$, $30 + 50 + 4$.

The methods of addition and subtraction within 100 are basically to replace one of the numbers with the sum of the room additions, then add the ones together, add the tens, and subtract one from the other, and the tens from the tens.

1. A system of exercises for learning to number numbers on the face.

1. Make the parentheses so that the result is correct:

$$30 - 7 + 3 = 20 \quad 20 - 9 - 9 = 2$$

$$40 - 6 + 2 = 32 \quad 6 + 7 - 5 = 8$$

2. Solve the problems by checking:

$$78 + 5 = 83 \quad 80 - 9 = 71 \quad 64 + 3 = 67$$

$$83-5 = 78 \quad 71 + 9 = 80 \quad 67-3 = 64$$

3. Using the result of the first example, calculate the result of the second example:

$$8 \times 6 = 48 \quad 9 \times 4 = 36 \quad 15 \times 2 = 30$$

$$6 \times 8 = 4 \times 9 \quad 2 \times 15$$

4. Replace the asterisks with the symbol $>$ or $=$:

$$6 \times 3 * 3 \times 6 \quad 7 \times 4 + 5 * 5 \times 7$$

$$2 \times 9 * 9 \times 3 \quad 8 \times 7 - 8 * 7 \times 8$$

5. Replace the asterisks with an unwritten action sign:

$$7 * 2 = 2 \times 7 \quad 3 \times 4 = 4 * 3 \quad 4 * 8 = 8 \times 4 \quad 6 * 5 = 5 \times 6 \quad 9 * 3 = 3 \times 9$$

In summary, by working on numbering numbers in a hundred, students learn to count objects in 1-100, add and write numbers, and compare one-digit and two-digit numbers.

Children develop the ability to compare numbers according to their position in the row, as well as to compare the number of decimals and units in a given number.

Knowledge and skills such as dividing numbers by 100 and their sequence, adding and writing numbers 21-100, and their decimal structure are strengthened.

Also, it takes a long time to work on the numbering of the face. As students explore this topic, they will develop skills and competencies about the different states and methods of addition and subtraction, multiplication and division, and properties within a face.

As a result of studying this topic, children learn to count, that is, to memorize the results of addition and subtraction of any number in 100 independently of the sum of numbers.

They also learn all the properties of multiplication and division.

Thus, the study of operations on the topic of "Hundreds" prepares students to quickly and easily perform written calculations of future calculations.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), BERDIYEV BAHODIR RAVSHANOVICH, (2020). "Teaching numbering within a hundred in elementary math classes (based on independent study)", **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 61 – 67. DOI: [www.doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.3993779](https://doi.org/10.5281/10.5281/zenodo.3993779), Special Issue, Issue: 2, Vol.: 2, Article: 7, Month: August, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

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